

*Microcystis aeruginosa* A0



*Microcystis aeruginosa* A50



*Microcystis aeruginosa* A100



Microcystis aeruginosa A200



Microcystis aeruginosa B0



*Microcystis aeruginosa* B50



*Microcystis aeruginosa* B100



Microcystis aeruginosa B200

